

EXPRESSING VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article compares groups of verbs in English and Uzbek languages. Their unique aspects, similarities and differences are revealed. The study of the verb group of words is inextricably linked with other groups of words.

Key words. Verb, important, written, the study, history, formation, languages, Uzbek, English

The verb is one of the active groups of words in all languages. The verb has a wide range of meanings, but mainly refers to a situation that conveys the concept of action and movement. The study of the verb group of words is inextricably linked with other groups of words. The largest group of words is also a verb. Mahmud Zamakhshari, a native of Khorezm, wrote several works on linguistics. The work "*Mukhabbatnama*" consists of five parts in the form of a noun, a verb, a conjunction, an inflection of a noun, an inflection of a verb. Created. Zamakhshari is the first scientist to group verbs according to their stem. Zamakhshari's place in the science of morphology is incomparable. In the work "*Tafsir*", which is one of the important written sources in the study of the history of the formation of the Old Uzbek literary language, words from the verbal family are used in many and colorful forms. Along with the features of the old Uzbek language, the features of the language of the ancient Turkic period are also shown. The grammatical meanings of person, tense and mood are expressed in the verb forms mentioned in the work.

This work uses the full and shortened forms of the verb, and also provides detailed information about the verb family. Our scientists noted the work "*Mukhabbatnama*", which embodied common Turkic features, as an example of the Old Uzbek written language of the literary language. Indeed, a number of morphological features were noted in the work. We can know this from the given verb conjugation information. Some verb forms in the "*Mukhabbatnama*" correspond to the old Uzbek language. But the grammatical devices used in some verb forms are characteristic of a much earlier language.

In the 14th century, there are two more works of unknown authorship, the first of which is the dictionary "*Tarjimon*". This dictionary consists of 76 pages and is divided into four parts. The first part is devoted to the noun, the second part is devoted to the issue of tenses of verbs and action nouns, the third part is devoted to form and tense, the fourth part is to the use of the word. The first three parts of this work are devoted to morphology, mainly studying a group of verbs. The second work is the work "*At-tuhfa*", in which the verb group is also studied in great detail. given.

The relationships between verbs, person, mood, and tense categories are examined in detail. This work reflects the relationship between the unknown, togetherness, inclusion and identity.

The peculiarity of English verbs is that in addition to semantic verbs, as in the Russian language, there are modal and auxiliary verbs, which are usually not translated in any way, but carry additional semantic load. One of the unique things about English verbs is that they can be regular or irregular. Irregular verbs differ from regular ones in that they are formed by adding a past participle.

To find out what form an irregular verb has in the past or future tense, you should use dictionaries, textbooks and special tables available on the Internet.

Linking verbs are basically nouns (*I'm a teacher*), features (*She's beautiful*), numerals (*It's 9 o'clock now*), pronoun (*It's me*) phrases and words expressing the meaning of the situation (*statistics, advertising links*) together form a noun participle. Based on the results of the analysis of linking verbs, the following types were identified: pure (*be*); special (expressing the meaning: *look, seem, appear, feel, taste*; insensitive: *become, get, grow, stay, hold, turn, go, run*). In addition, linking verbs can express independent meaning; such linking verbs are still used today and are formed from independent verbs.

For example: *To be or not to be, that is the question.* (Shakespeare) – Used as an independent verb.

In Uzbek, some linguists combine these two terms (conjunction and auxiliary verb) into one term and use it as an "incomplete verb".¹ Accordingly, imperfective verbs in the Uzbek language *it was, it was* organizes. It is also noted that in the Uzbek language an independent verb can become a conjunction and an auxiliary verb depending on the context.

For example, the independent verb *edi* in Uzbek is used as a linking verb in the first of the following sentences and as an auxiliary verb in the second:

U yosh edi; U uyimizga kelgan edi.

First of all, the members of a gradational series formed from verbal lexemes do not consist of one word in their structure, but are manifested by a variety of verbs in their structure.

Verbs have a simple structure (*go, freeze*), pair (*he took and gave*), repeated (*he read and read and wrote and wrote*) and system (*to be dissatisfied, to offer*) is divided into verbs. Simple verbs, in turn, have a root (*go, study*) and passive verbs (*freeze, evaporate*) separated.

Graduation lines can be composed of all of the above types of verbs. Verbs differ in their structure from other groups of words. With the help of basic verbs such as *do, be, be* in combination with other groups of words, complex verbs are formed that reflect one meaning: *give, offer, agree*. Unlike gradations in other groups of words, one gradation of verbs can only include verbal lexemes of the same or different structure.² It is even possible to use phraseological units that differ in meaning from lexical units that continue the gradation series and complement them. Lexemes with synonyms and antonyms can participate in a gradational series formed from verbs, since gradonymy is manifested both by words with similar meanings and words with opposite meanings.

Another feature of English verbs is personal and impersonal presence of verbs. Personal verbs act as predicates when they are the subject of a sentence. Impersonal verbs

¹ Khozhiev A.P. Imperfect verb. - T.: Nauka, 1970. - T. 8; HOT. - Modern Uzbek literary language. Part I. – T.: Science, 1966. - B. 320.

² Karimov I.A. The perfect generation is the basis for the development of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1998. - 64 p.

include, for example, participles. They rarely act as a predicate; they carry out the rest of the sentence.

The distinctive features of English verbs include the way they are formed. Verbs are simple, complex and derivative. Simple words consist only of the root and the ending of the word, for example: *beat - urmoq*. Complex verbs are formed by adding the stems of words, for example: *grow up - o'smoq*. In addition to roots, regular verbs also have adverbs. Example: *I do not like*.

When learning English, you should devote a lot of time to the verb to be, which is already its feature. It performs four functions, often acting as a semantic verb and a linking verb. Not every sentence in English can be composed without a verb, so existence is not a semantic verb and exists where there is a compound nominal predicate, e.g. *I am a student*, in Uzbek translated as "*Men talabaman*"

A verb is a group of words that express an action, state or process and have tense, mood, proportion, perfect, modality and other similar grammatical features. Verbs are words that express action. In grammar, the meaning of action is very broad, it is *run, swim, sit, stand* includes actions expressed by verbs such as *Surprise, worry* mental changes expressed by verbs such as, *bloom, grow* biological phenomena and similar actions and events expressed by verbs such as Apart from the fact that all of the above have certain forms, they all have a common aspect in that they are events that occur over time. A verb is an independent set of words expressing an action, state or process, i.e. the appearance or change of a certain characteristic. All of these verb-specific meanings go back to the general meaning of action, which helps distinguish it from other groups of words. How Y.S. According to Maslov, a verb is a group of words that expresses the grammatical meaning of an action, a feature that occurs in time.

There are similarities and differences in the declension of verbs in English and Uzbek languages. The indicative mood in the Uzbek language corresponds to the mood of the message, and the imperative mood corresponds to the mood of the command. But in English there is no mood similar to the objective mood in Uzbek, so we can compare its meaning with the indicative mood (the mood of the message). For example: *I want to be a teacher*.

The important thing is that the verb reflects the characteristics of an action occurring in a certain period of time. These features are manifested in the personal forms of the verb, and therefore the syntactic function of the personal forms of the verb should be used only as a predicate in a sentence. The system of verb exchange is much richer and more colorful than in other groups of words. This is not only a synthetic method, typical of inflected languages, but also has a formative addition to the root or analytical method. It should be noted that the verb is the only group of words that has analytical forms. If you pay special attention to the system of changing the words of verbs, you can see that there are very few verbs with suffixes formed by the affixation method, and there are much more complex verbs formed by the conversion method.

Verbs show action (*walk, run, write*) or availability status (*be, feel, smell and seem*) shows. Verbs have several characteristics: form, tense, person, number, voice and mood. Some verbs can stand alone in a sentence; the remaining verbs are auxiliary verbs. Auxiliary verbs *do, be, have* forms of words or *must/will, may/should, will/can/should* va *can/can* words. They combine with other verbs to form a complete verb phrase (for example, *slept*).

The remaining verbs are called linking verbs. Linking verbs connect the subject of a sentence to the following description. Linking verbs include forms of the verb *be* and verbs such as “*look*”, “*appear*”, “*grow*”, “*stay*”, “*stay*”, “*prove*”, “*feel*”, “*look*”, “*smell*”, “*sound*” and “*eat*.” English also has modal verbs. Special attention is paid to them, since these parts of speech differ from other English verbs in a number of features. They are indicators of the nature of the action and are used together with semantic verbs. For example, a modal verb should express a request to perform an action. I am going to school. I have to go to school. Modal verbs never *-ing*, *-s va -es* there will be no end. In some cases, modal verbs may be replaced by their equivalents or equivalent universal verbs. Equivalents are usually used instead of past and future modal verbs.

Examples of gradation series whose poles are opposite to each other: *start* → *continue* → *finish*. Complex verbs make up a large part of the composition of verbs and express semantically similar or contradictory meanings, so their participation in the ranking series is important.³ In addition to pure synonyms and antonyms, there are collocations and collocations, stylistic synonyms and antonyms, and contextual synonyms. Therefore, when forming a ranking series, not only simple and complex verbs are used, but also phrasal verbs according to the structure of the verbs. For example, *move* → *move* → *slide* → *push* → *step/stride* → *walk* → *speed up* → *scurry* → *run* → *swing* → *fly like a snail* in the ranking⁴ Together with simple verbs, the phrase *fly like a whirlwind* is also used to express an increasing pace of movement.

In English, according to their structure, verbs are divided into simple (*move*, *walk*), passive and complex verbs. In addition to simple verbs, the formed gradation of the English language also includes expressions and idioms.

For example, *budge* → *move* → *move* → *move* → *walk* → *run* → *run* → *jog* → *trot* → *gallop* → *race* → *run* if the gradational sequence consists only of pure verbs, *work* → *beaver away* → *toil* → *slave* → *keep working* → *toil (away)* → *keep your nose to the grindstone* in the gradonymic series *beaver away*, *slave away*, *continue*, *harass (away)* Phrases used here include the idiom “keep your nose to the grindstone.”⁵

As another important feature of the formation of ranking series, it can be noted that one ranked lexeme or phrase can participate in more than one ranking series. This lexeme or phrase can be included in various gradonymic series, taking into account its meanings and the scope of its use.⁶

For example, 1) *stroll* → *walk* → *wander*;

2) *move* → *move* → *move* → *step* → *walk* → *speed up* → *scurry* → *run* → *swing* → *fly* the verb to go participates in gradational lines. The first row was ranked according to walking over long distances, and the second row formed a gradational row according to increasing walking tempo. Similar gradations exist in the English language. We can see this with the example of the verb *walk*.⁷

³ Becker T. Backformation, crossformation and “bracketing paradoxes” in paradigmatic morphology // Yearbook of Morphology. - London: Arnold, 2003.-P. 1-25.

⁴ Blokh M.Yu. Course of theoretical grammar of the English language. M.: Foreign Languages Publishing House, 1983. – 379 p.

⁵ Ilyish B.A. The structure of Modern English. – L.: Education, 1971. – 365 p.

⁶ John E. Warriner Frans Geriffith Grammar and Composition of the English Language. -USA. 1977. - 471 p.

⁷ Gordon E.M. Krylova I.P. A Grammar of present-day English – M.: Higher School, 1986. - 429 p.

1) *walk* → *step* → *trail* → *hike* → *hike*;

2) *budge* → *move* → *move* → *move* → *walk* → *run* → *jog* → *jog* → *trot* → *gallop* → *race* → *run*.

Here the verb to go is presented in two different gradations according to the above characteristics.

In the examples above *go* and *go* Verbs formed different gradational series in terms of duration and increasing action in its meaning. *Listen* → *listen* → *listen and hear* → *know/know* → *learn* → *check* the rumor token in the rank strings is involved in two different meanings in both strings. *Listen* → *hear* → *listen* → *listen* in the gradonymic series, to hear means to perceive sounds with the ear and participated in gradations of increasing attentiveness when perceiving sounds. The lexeme *here* in the second gradonymic line creates a gradation of increasing reliability of information in the contextual meaning of awareness of information.

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